

One Mobile Phone Model of Chinese Medical Qigong Therapies

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Abstract

Background: Qigong is one characteristic therapy of traditional Chinese medicine(TCM), and it has benefited more and more. However, to our best knowledge, the physical model of Qigong therapies remains unknown.

Method: Based on the progress of modern science, one physical model of Qigong therapy-mobile phone model is presented.

Discussions: The main points of the model are: one normal healthy person is just like one mobile phone which is communicating well in the net, the internal Qi of the person is just like the standing electromagnetic waves inside of the mobile phone, and the external Qi is just like the travelling electromagnetic waves outside of it; the best Qigong state of one healthy person is considered just like one continuing optimal mobile phone, with development one generation by one generation and with strong signal communicating well in net, not like one fixed to one generation. The reason of one person is sick is the electromagnetic waves inside of the person deviates from standing waves or the electromagnetic waves outside deviates from travelling waves. It is the first step to correct the deviation for one patient to cultivate Qigong and finally to get the optimal state of integrating the Three Adjustments into one. The rationality of the mobile phone model and the essence of Qi in the model are discussed.

Introduction

Qigong is one characteristic therapy of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) [1-3], is one part of natural medicine, has a long history and a wide scope of application [1]. In general, It has also partly attributes to the diseases out of its indications, however, not of its contradictions [1]. Since it was recognized as one traditional and complementary medicine by world health organization(WHO) [4], in the world, it has been paid attention and studied more and more in medicines [5-9], in physiology [10-13], in biochemistry [14-16], in psychology [17-20], in physical education [21-23], in physics [24-27], and in some comprehensive subjects [28-31]. Its benefits has been reported more and more [19, 32-35]. Qigong therapies has two basic methods: one is internal Qigong [1]in which the patients practice themselves to get health after mastering suitable Qigong forms under professional help. Internal Qigong is the primary method, in reported researches, its benefits in the help to heal cancers [32, 36-38], to heal fatigues [39-41], to heal Parkinson's diseases [42-43], to heal stroke [44] , to heal Traumatic brain injury (TBI)

[45] , to heal HIV [46], to heal diseases on COVID-19's [47-48], to heal drug addiction [49], to heal pains [50-52] and so on. The other is external Qigong [1], in which the patients only follow the orders of therapists and are treated by emitted Qi from the Qigong master, its benefits in the healing of cancers [53], in the healing of osteoarthritis of the knee [6]. The doctrines of Yin-Yang and Five-elements, the internal organ meridians and various others are characteristic theory of Qigong therapies in TCM [1]. Psychological effects of Qigong [1, 17], physiological effects of it [1, 10-13], biochemical and immunological effects [1, 14-15], and physical effects [1] of it can show the theoretical evidences of modern science. Adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing, adjustment of mind, Integrating the Three Adjustments into one is the basic operations of Qigong practice and the state of integrating the Three Adjustments into one is the aim of Qigong practice [1]. In other words, the state of integrating the Three Adjustments into one is "de dao" [17]. The body-mind medicine about Qigong between the east and the west is one unit from the viewpoint of the integration of

More Information

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Keywords:

Qigong therapy, mobile phone model, standing electromagnetic waves, travelling electromagnetic waves, Qi.

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psychology, TCM, physical education [30]. Some researchers considered Qigong as one of biofeedback therapies [11, 54-55]. As well known, physics is the common base of natural science except for mathematics, It is natural obvious, that physics has the basic role in Qigong therapies. However, to our best knowledge, the physical model of Qigong therapies remains unknown. External Qi of Qigong results from the emission of internal Qi, the external Qi and internal Qi have the similar natural properties [1]. Internal Qi always circulates in the system of meridians [30]. Meridians is electromagnetic field propagating in ordered medium just like human tissues [56]. The known researches has shown, almost all living cells can transmit and receive electromagnetic fields and waves from kHz to visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum [57]. In this research, one physical model has been present, and the discussions on its rationality have also been given.

Method

Mobile Phone Model of Qigong Therapies

One normal healthy person is just like one mobile phone which is communicating well in the net, the internal Qi of the person is just like the standing electromagnetic waves inside of the mobile phone, and the external Qi is just like the travelling electromagnetic waves outside of it. One characteristic part of the standing electromagnetic waves is that most energy of it doesn't travel, only a few part energy of it does do. One characteristic part of the travelling electromagnetic waves is that all energy except of loss of it always does travel. Internal Qi or external Qi of one patient is not normal just like the standing electromagnetic waves or the travelling electromagnetic waves of one mobile phone are not normal. One patient is healthy again through internal Qigong or external Qigong just like one mobile phone is from abnormal state to the normal state with standing electromagnetic waves inside of it and travelling electromagnetic waves outside of it. The internal Qi of one normal healthy person is standing electromagnetic waves which is full of the internal organ meridians. Once the internal Qi is formed finally as a whole, it is a dynamic equilibrium state relatively. The external Qi is the emission of internal Qi from the acupuncture points of one's body. The external Qi is travelling electromagnetic waves.

The mobile phones can communicate because the antennas inside of them can transmit and receive electromagnetic waves. The nearer part surrounding the working antennas is full of standing electromagnetic waves which is inside of the mobile phones. The further part of the working antennas is travelling electromagnetic waves which is outside of the mobile phones to communicate. Based on biophysics, almost all living cells can transmit and

receive electromagnetic fields and waves from kHz to visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum [57]. In other words, long waves, microwaves, infrared waves, visible light waves are all in the range, and Terahertz waves which is between the microwaves and infrared waves is also in the range. When the electromagnetic waves emitted from the living cells arrive in the surface of the body and bones which can be considered as the electromagnetic interfaces, the waves can be reflected rounds and rounds, finally the standing electromagnetic waves as the internal Qi is formed. Because of the surface of the body is not perfect electromagnetic interface, some standing electromagnetic waves can be emitted and form the external Qi, based on the mechanism of slotted antennas, which is travelling electromagnetic waves.

Discussions

The Coincidence between the Mobile Phone Model and the Requirement of Three Adjustments into One

"Qigong is the skill of body-mind exercise that integrates body, breath, and mind adjustments into one" [1]. Is it coincident between the mobile phone model and the requirement of Three Adjustments into one? The meaning of one in "Three Adjustments into one" is the optimal living state or "heaven and men integrated into one" [1]. Almost all living cells can transmit and receive electromagnetic fields and waves, which can be considered as antennas or sources of the fields and waves [57]. The cells that organize muscles and organs just like heart, intestines, stomach, and brain are all sources of electromagnetic waves, so the essence of adjustment of body is adjustment of electromagnetic fields and waves from the viewpoint of the mobile phone model. Because the activity of nerve cells in adjustment of mind is indivisible, the essence of adjustment of mind is adjustment of electromagnetic fields and waves. Because adjustment of breathing and making sounds in the course is unable without the help of adjustment of mind, the essence of adjustment of breathing is adjustment of electromagnetic fields and waves. That is to say, the essence of Three Adjustments are all adjustments of electromagnetic fields and waves. What is the optimal state or the aim of Qigong cultivation from the viewpoint of the mobile phone mode? The state is full of standing electromagnetic waves in the body and travelling electromagnetic waves out of the body, just like one mobile phone which is communicating well in the net. Electromagnetic waves inside and outside of the mobile phone are emitted by the antenna in it. The according software and other hardware besides of the cell to provide energy are used to support the mobile phone to work. If the electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one mobile phone, is supposed as the Qi of one healthy person, the cells to provide energy and other hardware is supposed as the body of one healthy

person, the according software is supposed as the mind, one mobile phone which is communicating well in the net can be supposed as one healthy person who is in the state of making integrating the Three Adjustments into one. From this, one can understand well the mobile phone model of Qigong therapies.

The Explanation of the State of Three Adjustments into One Based on the Mobile Phone Model

Adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing, adjustment of mind, Integrating the Three Adjustments into one or heaven and men integrated into one, is the state of Qigong. It is the optimal living state. In this state, the difference among the Three Adjustments can not be found, while this state is not fixed, is full of vitality and continues to develop [1]. In other words, the state of Three Adjustments into one is one dynamic equilibrium state relatively. This state can be gotten by one normal healthy person or one patient through Qigong cultivation. To get the state, there are two basic methods: one is consolidating method, which is getting the Three Adjustments free one by one and then integrating the Three Adjustments into one step by step; the other is extending method, which is getting any one of the Three Adjustments to the most perfect [1]. Obviously, there is a long course of Qigong cultivation for one ordinary person to get Qigong state. However, one patient gets healthy surely when s/he gets the state. From the viewpoint of mobile phone model, when one person is in the Qigong state and doesn't emit external Qi, the standing electromagnetic waves inside of the person is dominant, just like one mobile phone is in free state. When one person is in the Qigong state and does external Qi, the travelling electromagnetic waves outside of the person is dominant, just like one mobile phone is in busy state. If one person gets the Qigong state, regardless the person does or not emit external Qi, the state is integrating the person's Qi and universal Qi [1] into one or integrating the electromagnetic waves inside and outside of the person including the cosmic microwave background [58] and other surrounding electromagnetic waves into one. The essence of the course, which one patient gets healthy by Qigong cultivation, is making the electromagnetic waves inside and outside of the patient from weak to strong, from communicating poor to well, from communicating locally to globally, until the standing electromagnetic waves are full inside of the patient and travelling electromagnetic waves are full outside of the person. From the viewpoint of the mobile phone model, the electromagnetic waves inside of ordinary healthy person is standing waves, and the electromagnetic waves outside is travelling waves. This is the same as one grand master of Qigong. The difference between one ordinary person and one grand master is the intensity of electromagnetic waves inside and outside of them. The intensity of the behind is

more stronger than that of the front. If one ordinary healthy person and one grand master of Qigong are all respectively considered as one mobile phone, the two phones all can communicate in the net, while signal of the ordinary healthy person is more weaker than the grand master. The reason of one person is sick is the electromagnetic waves inside of the person deviates from standing waves or the electromagnetic waves outside deviates from travelling waves. It is the first step to correct the deviation for one patient to cultivate Qigong and finally to get the optimal state of integrating the Three Adjustments into one. It is not the best, if the state is only considered just like one mobile phone with strong signal communicating well in net. The best is that the state is considered just like one continuing optimal mobile phone, with development one generation by one generation and with strong signal communicating well in net, not like one fixed to one generation.

The Explanation of the Qi Sensation Based on the Mobile Phone Model

Qi sensation is the sensing by one that Qi inside of one's body is moving or Qi is in and out of one's surface [1]. For example, the sensation that internal Qi descends to the lower elixir or the sensation that Qi exchanges with the surrounding environment and universe through the sweat pores in body breathing. Some Qigong forms, for example, Genuine Qi Circulation Method [1], get healthy benefits through following Qi sensation. Getting Qi sensation is mostly helpful for one to practice Qigong. According to the mobile phone model, Qi sensation is like one directly senses Qi or electromagnetic waves inside or outside of one's body. However, it is not real. Because the special receptors of electromagnetic fields and waves have not been discovered except of visual receptors in one's eyes. From the view point of modern science, Qi sensation is one indirect effect which is one comprehensive sense of all kinds of cells, working in Qigong practice, just like incited antennas. According to the mechanism of antennas, electromagnetic waves emitted or received in space by the antennas are not random. Qi sensation in space is not random for Qi is electromagnetic waves based on the mobile phone model. Qi sensation in practicing Genuine Qi Circulation Method [1]. Is one good example in explaining this.

The Explanation of Benefits of Qigong Based on the Mobile Phone Model

Some normal reactions are benefits of Qigong during integrating the Three Adjustments into one, for examples, "pulsations and sensations" reaction, "meridians and collaterals" reaction, physiological and functional reactions, reactions of entering the tranquil meditation state, etc [1]. The explanation of benefits of Qigong based on the mobile phone model is the results of excitation and progression by each of body, mind,

and Qi(electromagnetic waves), during integrating the Three Adjustments into one is realized and the whole electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one's body are found.

The explanation of holism of Qigong therapy based on the mobile phone model

All diseases in the scope of indications of Qigong therapy [1] can be healed through a right and required time of internal Qigong practice. In other words, the health of whole body will come and integrating the Three Adjustments into one is realized. For the internal relations among adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing, adjustment of mind, one gets completely health, once the Three Adjustments into one is realized, regardless of one chooses adjustment of body, or adjustment of breathing, or adjustment of mind as the first step for Qigong practice, and regardless of Three Adjustments is how to be arranged in one's practice. Once the standing electromagnetic waves are full inside of the patient and travelling electromagnetic waves are full outside of her or him. The electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one's body is a whole. That is the explanation of holism of Qigong based on the mobile phone model. The state of which the electromagnetic waves inside of one's body is standing waves and the electromagnetic waves outside of one's body is travelling waves, is sufficient and communicating well with Qi, called healthy state. The standing electromagnetic waves are composed two parts, one is the pure standing waves which is located according to part of one's body, the other is circulating in the body. Travelling waves which are composed a whole with the standing waves are from acupuncture points of one's body.

The Explanation of Dynamic Healthy State of One's Full Life Based on the Mobile Phone Model

If one fertilized egg is normal, the electromagnetic waves inside and outside of it are normal. If the whole developing course in uterus and the birth of infant are normal, the electromagnetic waves inside of the born are standing waves and the electromagnetic waves outside are travelling waves according to the mobile phone model. It is just like one normal mobile phone is assembled by component elements that one normal fertilized egg develops into one healthy infant. It is just like one normal mobile phone is moved away from one factory that one healthy infant is born. If one baby is always normal in the whole growing course, the electromagnetic waves inside of the baby are always standing waves and the electromagnetic waves outside of her or him are always travelling waves according to the mobile phone model. However, the space full of electromagnetic waves is wider and wider in the growing course, and the intensity of electromagnetic waves is stronger and stronger. When one person is older and older, weaker and weaker, if the person is

normal and healthy, the electromagnetic waves inside of the person are always standing waves and the electromagnetic waves outside of her or him are always travelling waves according to the mobile phone model. However the intensity of electromagnetic waves inside and outside of the person is weaker and weaker, it is just like one normal mobile phone may be used still, though older and older, however, the electromagnetic waves the phone can transmit and receive are weaker and weaker.

The Mechanism of Healing Based on the Mobile Phone Model

What is the mechanism if the unhealthy Qi of one patient may be just like as electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one mobile phone not communicating well in net, and if the power cell and other hard ware may be just like the body of the patient, and if the according soft ware may be just like the mind of the patient? If one patient chooses one internal Qigong [1] to heal herself or himself, one seed appears naturally in his or her mind which internal Qigong can heal herself or himself. This is just like as one mobile phone is fixed one antivirus and clearing software. With the days of Qigong practice go, the seed will be more active under the help of suggestion by the patient herself or himself. This is the mechanism of healing by adjustment of mind. When it appears naturally for one patient to require to adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing, adjustment of mind in her or his mind, the effects of adjustment of mind are direct and the effects of adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing are indirect. This is just like as software in one phone is fixed some parts to control. For all active cells can be thought as antennas to transmit and receive electromagnetic waves [57], the resources can be adjusted in the course of adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing. It is the mechanism of healing oneself by internal Qigong to make electromagnetic waves inside the body of the patient are standing waves and electromagnetic waves outside the body of the patient are traveling waves. This is realized by direct adjustment the resources of electromagnetic waves through adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing and by indirect adjustment of mind. The change of electromagnetic waves surrounding one antenna can have different effects on it, the normal is to receive signal, for example, to answer one telephone, and the abnormal is disturbing. The external Qigong therapy [1] is just like to answer one telephone. External Qi or electromagnetic traveling waves from one Qigong master will be reflected and refracted based on the mobile phone model and propagating characters of electromagnetic waves when arriving on the body of one patient. The external Qi or electromagnetic waves are very stronger than that of one ordinary person or surroundings. When the

refractive part of external Qi or electromagnetic waves enters into the body of one patient and meets the resonant conditions, just like many tuning forks resonated, the intensity of the Qi or electromagnetic waves will be enhanced and transmitted. The course of refraction and reflection will last as long as the master transmits external Qi. For the frequencies of electromagnetic waves are not changed during the reflection and refraction, the electromagnetic standing waves inside of one patient and the electromagnetic traveling waves outside of the patient with the same frequencies as transmitted by the master will appear after a certain time. This is the mechanism of external Qigong therapy based on the mobile phone model. For the velocity of electromagnetic waves is 30, 000 kilometers per second, the time is very short in theory. The time in fact also depends on the professional ability of the master and the ability of the patient to receive Qi or electromagnetic waves.

The Explanation of Healing Cancers Based on the Mobile Phone Model

Cancers is one very effective kind in the scope of indications of Qigong therapy [32, 36-38]. If one patient with cancers chooses internal Qigong therapy, after one course or some courses of practice, she or he will get satisfactory benefits [1]. The mechanism of healing cancers through internal Qigong therapy [1] is recovering the state of electromagnetic standing waves inside of one patient and electromagnetic traveling waves outside of the patient from deviation of it by adjustment her or his body, breath and mind. The mechanism of healing cancers through external Qigong therapy [1] is also recovering the state of electromagnetic standing waves inside of one patient and electromagnetic traveling waves outside of the patient from deviation of it. However, there are two differences between the internal and external Qigong therapy. The one difference is the recovering is from the inside to the outside for the internal therapy, and it is just opposite for the external. For the external Qigong therapy, the Qi or electromagnetic waves inside of one patient can be changed only after the Qi or electromagnetic waves outside changed. The other difference is the time of external Qigong therapy is much shorter usually than the internal Qigong therapy. For in the course of internal Qigong therapy, one patient with cancers has to enhance the required Qi or electromagnetic waves with her or his weak body and mind, however, in the course of external Qigong therapy, one patient with cancers only receives the strong Qi or electromagnetic waves transmitted by the master. Of course, one patient has to have the good state to receive Qi or electromagnetic waves.

The Explanation of Physical Effects of External Qigong Based on the Mobile Phone Model

The physical effects of external Qigong are mainly composed of the infrared effect, the radiation effect of the photons, the magnetic field effect, the electronic field effect, the effect of sound waves and the effect of Terahertz waves, etc. [1, 59]. The scope of electromagnetic waves is very wide, and it can be divided into 3 bands in general. The first band is wireless electronic waves, the second is light waves, and the third is radiation. Every bands can be divided continually. The first can be divided into long waves, middle waves, short waves and microwaves. The second can be divided into infrared waves, visual waves and ultraviolet waves. Terahertz waves are between microwaves and infrared waves. The electronic field effect and the magnetic field effect of external Qigong are natural if the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves for electromagnetic waves is one unit of electronic fields and magnetic fields. Characters of electromagnetic waves is one unit of waves and particles. Wireless electronic waves usually can be considered as waves. Light waves and Terahertz waves have to be considered as not only waves but also particles often. This also called wave particle duality. The infrared effect, the radiation effect of the photons, the effect of Terahertz waves can be explained based on the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves when considered the wave particle duality of electromagnetic waves. The effect of sound waves obviously can not be explained directly based on the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves. However, when one master transmits Qi, with mechanical vibration of some parts in the body of the master produced, sound waves appear naturally. For external Qi is from internal Qi [1], internal Qi can has some different effects in the body from the normal state to transmitting Qi state, for example, the changes of heart rate, which sometimes can make mechanical vibration and sound waves. In other words, the effect of sound waves is not the natural effect of external Qi and sound waves is not the essence of Qi. This is consistent with the point of Qi theory of TCM that Qi is full of all universe [1, 2]. Obviously, sound waves can not be considered as Qi, for it can not exist in vacuum.

The Virtues and Shortcomings of the Mobile Phone Model

The mobile phone model is one physical model. In this model, not only the mechanism of Qigong therapy is explained, but also the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves is given. This model can also answer many theoretical questions based on TCM and many practical phenomena in Qigong practice. These are virtues of the mobile phone model. However, mobile phone is just one artificial, even smarter and smarter one. Some characters of human beings can not be followed by

mobile phones for ever, and the conditions to be sure of one person's health are further complex than ones to be sure of one mobile's good communication in net, so the model can not imitate many characters of Qigong therapy. For example, the self-actuation [1] is one. If one patient has determined to choose Qigong therapy, s/he can actively do everything for integrating the Three Adjustments into one to get her or his health, and will not stop until success. One mobile phone can not do this for ever.

The Discussions on the Model of the Essence of Qi is Electromagnetic Waves

The definition of "qigong" is contradictory in the modern research of Qigong therapy, and there are three points mainly: the first is that it is considered only as one special psychic therapy with traditional Chinese culture; the second is that it is one technique or way to regulate life energy; the third is that it is the skill of body-mind exercise that integrating body, breath, and mind adjustment into one [1]. The essence of external Qi is contradictory, and there are three points mainly: the first is that it is one physical energy, the physical energy may be sound, light, electromagnetic waves, particles or may be one unknown energy; the second is that the effects of external Qi is only psychic, in other words, the external Qi does not exist in real; the third is that external Qi not only exist in real but also it has psychic effects [1]. From these one can see that the controversy of definition of Qigong is consistent with the controversy of the essence of external Qi, that is to say, whether external Qi exists or not in real. For external Qi is from internal Qi [1], whether external Qi exists or not in real is whether Qi including internal Qi and external Qi exist or not. According to the progression on this research [24, 59], the points in the mobile phone model are present: the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves, the essence of internal Qi is electromagnetic standing waves, the essence of external Qi is electromagnetic traveling waves, and electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one person is one unit. Through the discussions above, the rightness of the points are given firstly. This is not enough. If the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves, the effects of external Qi are biological ones of electromagnetic waves. One conclusion can be given from this: all effects of external Qi are same as all biological effects of according electromagnetic waves. These are breakthroughs to prove the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves. To show the essence of internal Qi is electromagnetic standing waves, theories and techniques on bioelectromagnetics including bioelectricity, such as electroencephalogram, electrocardiogram and electromyography; biomagnetics, such as magnetoencephalogram; biophotonics and radiobiology have to be used to the research. After more evidences and more summaries to

verify it appear, the truth of that the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves can be showed. The characters of whole scope of electromagnetic waves are clear in general with the development of theory and technique of Terhertz wave. If the truth of that the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves is showed one day, the all effects of Qi is the same as electromagnetic waves, these can well contribute to the research of Qigong therapy theory and give a new bridge to connect TCM and modern medicine. If the truth of that the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves is showed one day, many characters of electromagnetic waves can be used in Qigong therapy to get better effects. For example, in the practice of external Qigong therapy, one master can make one convenient Qi field using the mechanism of antenna arrays. The other explorations on the essence of Qi [59, 60] are present.

Summary and limitations

The article presents one model of Qigong therapy, the mobile phone model. In the model, these contents are composed of: the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves, the essence of internal Qi is electromagnetic standing waves, the essence of external Qi is electromagnetic traveling waves, and electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one person is one unit; the coincidence between the model and the requirement of Three Adjustments into one; the explanation of the state of Three Adjustments into one based on the model; the explanation of the Qi sensation based on the model; the explanation of holism of Qigong therapy based on the model; the explanation of dynamic healthy state of one's full life based on the model; the mechanism of healing based on the model; the explanation of healing cancers based on the model; the explanation of physical effects of external Qigong based on the model; the virtues and shortcomings of the model; the discussions on the essence of Qi is electromagnetic waves.

The article only gives a limited explorations of the mobile phone model in Chinese medical Qigong and more explorations in the scope of TCM is one future work; the other is to find one concrete model of the whole electromagnetic waves inside and outside of one body based on the sources of electromagnetic waves in the body.

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